

Grading System for Rice International Trade (Table 1) as:

Long size grains and bold shape: Italpatna, Bahia/ IR52-21A, Betis, and Gema/ Sequial96:

Medium size grain and round shape: Bahia, Niva, Jucar, and Balilla/Sollana;

Medium size grain and bold shape: Sequial.

All varieties and breeding lines had low amylose content (<20%) and high alkali spreading value (6-7 when immersed in 11 ml of 1.4% KOH) (Table 2). Bahia/IR52-21A has very

good eating quality (N index) related to high cooking stability.

Cooked grains of Italpatna, Gema/ Sequial 96. and Bahia/ IR52-21 A had the stability and cohesiveness for the best eating quality. ■

Table 1. Milling quality and grain characteristics of some rice varieties grown in Spain.^a

Variety	Grain size and shape (milled rice)				Milling yield	
	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Length-width ratio	Whole kernel (head) rice (70)	Total milled rice (%)
Bahia	5.5 a	3.0 a	2.1 a	1.8 a	57.3 a	68.9 ab
Sequial	5.4 a	2.7 b	1.8 b	2.0 b	59.6 a	70.4 c
Niva	5.4 a	2.9 c	2.0 c	1.9 a	59.3 a	69.5 a
Júcar	5.4 a	2.9 c	2.0 c	1.8 a	58.3 a	67.2 d
Balilla/Sollana	5.1 b	3.1 d	2.1 a	1.7 c	57.8 a	67.0 d
Italpatna	6.5 c	2.5 e	1.8 b	2.6 d	48.5 b	68.3 bc
Betis	6.2 d	2.6 f	1.8 d	2.3 e	61.2 a	69.5 a
Gema/Sequial 96	6.4 c	2.7 b	1.8 d	2.3 e	56.7 a	68.7 b
Bahia/IR52-21A	6.1 d	2.9 c	2.0 c	2.1 f	50.8 b	67.7 de

^a Means of 4 replications. In a column, values with common letters are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Table 2. Cooking and eating qualities of some rice varieties grown in Spain.^a

Variety	Amylose content (% d.b.)	Alkali spreading value	N index ^b	Gelatinization time (min)	Water uptake (mg/mm ²)	Elongation ratio (%)	Eating quality characteristics ^c		
							Cohesiveness	Acceptability	Stability (not fracturability)
Bahia	19.4 ab	6.0 ab	806 d	17.7 a	1.3 ab	54.5 a	8 a	6 a	6 a
Sequial	18.5 b	5.4 c	662 a	16.6 b	1.2 b	38.0 c	8 a	6 a	6 a
Niva	19.8 ab	6.0 ab	751 c	17.7 a	1.2 b	50.5 b	8 a	5 a	5 a
Júcar	19.3 ab	6.1 ab	812 d	16.9 b	1.2 b	53.7 a	8 a	6 a	6 a
Balilla/Sollana	20.5 a	6.2 a	708 b	17.1 b	1.3 ab	49.4 b	8 a	6 a	4 a
Italpatna	18.7 b	6.1 ab	740 c	15.0 c	1.3 ab	39.6 c	9 b	8 b	8 b
Betis	17.2 c	5.9 ab	800 d	15.3 c	1.3 b	33.3 d	8 a	5 a	5 a
Gema/Sequial 96	17.2 c	5.9 b	792 d	15.4 c	1.2 b	30.5 e	9 b	8 b	8 b
Bahia/IR52-21A	20.1 a	5.9 ab	921 e	18.4 d	1.4 a	53.9 a	9 b	8 b	8 b

^a Means of 4 replications. In a column, values with common letters are not significantly different at the 5% level ^bAbsorbance at 550 nm of alkali-soluble proteins of whole grain rice by biuret test per gram of rice; protein content of the outermost layer, extracted by alkali. ^cScale 1 to 9 is adopted with 9 = highest intensity character.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Reaction of rice varieties to stem nematodes in Vietnam

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The coleoptile inoculation method, with 10 adult nematodes (*Ditylenchus angustatus*) per germinated seed, was used to screen 1,197 varieties and cultivars in 1979-81. After inoculation and 48-hour

incubation in a moisture-saturated atmosphere at 28-30° C, 40 seedlings of each variety were transplanted at 10 seedlings/ pot. Pots were placed in a partly shaded greenhouse, 80-90% relative humidity, and 28-30°C temperature.

Degrees of infestation were classified 30 days after inoculation as very slight (disease incidence below 20%), slight (20-40%), moderate (41-60%), severe (61-80%), and very severe (over 80%).

Of 34 deepwater varieties, 3 had

slight, 24 moderate, and 7 severe infestation.

Of 22 rainfed varieties, 2 had very slight, 4 slight, 10 moderate, and 6 severe infestation.

Of 145 early maturity local varieties, 4 had slight, 107 moderate, 31 severe, and 3 very severe infestation.

Of 368 medium maturity local varieties, 3 had very slight, 79 slight, 175 moderate, 104 severe, and 7 very severe infestation.

Of 502 late maturity local varieties, 7 had very slight, 94 slight, 274 moderate, 126 severe, and 1 very severe infestation.

Of 126 high-yielding improved varieties or cultivars, 4 had very slight infestation (IR9 129-393-3-1-2, IR9 129-169-3-

2-2, IR9224-117-2-3-1 and IR2307-247-2-2-3). The rest had moderate to very severe infestation. ■

Yield loss due to bacterial leaf blight

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Bacterial blight damage was assessed in a field planted with variety Jaya in

Yield differences in bacterial blight-infected rice in Haryana, India.

Infection grade	1	3	5	7	9
Yield loss (%)	6.3	12.3	21	31.6	36.8

Gobindgarh village, Kurukshetra district, during 1981 kharif. The first blight symptoms were observed on 17 August. The disease continued to spread until the first week of September. Plants with different grades of infection by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice

were tagged the last week of August at 4-5 growth stage of the crop. For each disease grade, 100 hills were harvested and yield was compared with yield from 100 healthy hills (see table). Yield loss occurred even at infection grade 1 and increased with grade of infection. ■

Potential sources of blast resistance for hilly regions in India

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Extensive screening for blast resistance in 1978-81 included more than 1,400 local hill rices, about 2,000 improved strains and promising advanced generation bulks from various research centers within India, and about 1,200 cultures from the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP), including the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN). Natural disease pressure is always extremely high at the experimental farms where screenings were carried out.

High tolerance materials from the preliminary screenings were tested under artificial epiphytotic conditions. Selected materials were also tested at Pithoragarh, Bhowali, Majhera, and Palampur in 1981. All promising entries were tested for neck blast reaction under Almora conditions.

Nineteen entries scored 2 or below (Standard Evaluation System for Rice) at more than 70% of the locations where IRBN has been tested under the IRTP, and conform to the requirements for potential sources of resistance for both leaf and neck blast. IR9292-21-1, VL8, Milyang 46, IR5908-84-2-3-3, IR5931-81-1-1, IR5031-P1p-4B, IR5908-84-2-2, Toride I, and Wagwag combine high blast resistance with medium short maturity and fair cold tolerance. Ta-

poo-choz, Camponi SML, Colombia 11, Dissihatif (73127), IR4547-6-2-5, and RP 1057-35-I-I have medium late maturity and some degree of cold tolerance. Tetep, IR1544-238-2-3, IR3273-339-2-5, and IR1416-128-5-8 also have high tolerance for sheath rot and leaf scald diseases. Except for IR3273-339-2-5, all the listed IR varieties seem to derive their resistance from Tetep.

VL8, Milyang 46, and IR9202-21-1 showed a combination of desirable agronomic features in addition to blast resistance. VL8, a japonica type with some tolerance for *Helminthosporium* disease and some insect pests, is already on the list of released varieties for the hilly regions of Uttar Pradesh. Sufficient quantities of seeds are being produced for immediate use. ■

Evaluation of rice cultivars for resistance to blast and brown spot diseases

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National Screening Nurseries (NSN) 1 and 2 and the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN) trials during 1981 kharif at Mandya evaluated 954 cultivars for resistance to leaf blast, neck blast, and brown spot diseases. Reactions were recorded under nursery and

transplanted conditions.

Of 386 cultivars screened in NSN 1, 31 showed combined resistance for leaf

blast, neck blast, and brown spot. Only 17 entries in NSN 2 and 17 in the IRBN trial showed combined resistance. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

An improved oviposition cage for rice stem borers

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In the old oviposition cages used to collect stem borer egg masses at IRRI,

many of the egg masses were laid on cage surfaces other than the one designated for oviposition. A new oviposition cage was constructed to force female moths of *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker), *C. polychrysus* (Meyrick), and *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker to oviposit on the desired substrate.